

Screen Time and Dry Eye in School-Aged Children: A Comparative Study Between High and Low Altitudes

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Abstract

Aim: This study aims to investigate the relationship between screen time and dry eye disease in school-age children living in regions of varying altitudes by assessing ocular symptoms, tear film stability, and tear production.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 398 school children aged 6-18 in Lucknow (low altitude) and Sikkim (high altitude) over a year. Data collection involved history-taking, OSDI questionnaires, and ocular examinations. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS.

Results: High-altitude residents showed decreased TBUT and tear production with increased screen time, while low-altitude residents maintained normal levels. Prolonged screen exposure led to more severe ocular discomfort in low-altitude individuals with p-value less than 0.05. Gender and age differences in screen time usage were also observed.

Conclusion: Research indicates that screen time and age impact eye health differently at varying altitudes. Children in high-altitude areas spend less time on screens but are at higher risk for eye issues like Dry Eye Disease. It is important to develop strategies to regulate screen time and address eye health concerns, particularly for children in high-altitude regions.

Key Words: Dry Eye Disease (DED), Computer vision syndrome (CVS), High altitude, low altitude, Tear break-up time (TBUT), Schirmer test and OSDI (Ocular surface index questionnaire)

Introduction

Dry eye disease, also known as keratoconjunctivitis sicca (KCS), is a multifaceted inflammatory condition that impacts the tear film by hindering the adequate lubrication provided by tears secreted by the eyes (Koh, S., & Rhee, M. K.,2021). The ocular manifestations arise from the disruption in the tear film's balance, located on the outermost layer of the cornea, which can be ascribed to either excessive evaporation or insufficient tear

production. This disruption in the tear film is believed to be initiated by abnormalities in the eyelids, variations in tear composition, or decreased blinking frequency due to prolonged exposure to screens (Bron, A. J. et al, 2017).

In recent times, the utilization of visual display terminals (VDTs) or digital screens has become a common practice among individuals of diverse age groups, whether for work or leisure activities. Nonetheless, this increasing dependence on digital screens has been identified as a significant contributing factor to the development of Dry Eye Disease (DED). This can be linked to the prolonged periods spent using VDTs in close proximity, resulting in a reduction in blinking frequency. Consequently, the tear film becomes more unstable and evaporates at a quicker rate, thereby worsening the symptoms of DED. (Bron, A. J. et al, 2017 and Alnahdi W. et al, 2022).

In the pediatric population, the causes, visual impairment, and treatment obstacles of DED differ significantly, akin to various chronic diseases. The use of electronic devices among children has surged in recent years, with reported usage varying greatly based on the children's age and geographical location. However, there is limited research on the prevalence of dry eye syndrome in young individuals who use electronic gadgets. A study in Korea found that excessive mobile phone use was a notable risk factor for dry eye disease (Moon, J. H. et al, 2016).

Recent research in Hong Kong has revealed that children are also experiencing frequent symptoms related to computer vision syndrome, such as neck and back pain. Additionally, there seems to be a link between higher cognitive strain and a reduced blink rate among these young individuals (Siu, D. C. H. et al, 2009). Scientific literature has emphasized that environmental factors like low oxygen levels, low humidity, strong winds, and intense ultraviolet light exposure at high altitudes can affect the ocular surface condition. However, there is a lack of research on the specific connection between different altitudes and the level of eye discomfort (Bingjie Liu, 2023).

The prevalence of dry eye, as reported by Al-beitz (2000) and Moss et al. (2000), ranges from 10.8% to 15.3% depending on the diagnostic criteria used. Nonetheless, there has been no comparative analysis conducted among Indian school children living at high and low altitudes to determine the prevalence of dry eye and its relationship with screen time. Therefore, the

main aim of this study was to investigate whether there is a link between screen usage duration and the occurrence of dry eye in school-age children residing at both high and low altitudes.

Methodology-

The research design included a cross-sectional approach with data collected through simple random sampling after obtaining ethical clearance. The informed consent forms were provided. The study was conducted in schools in Lucknow and Sikkim from March 2023 to April 2024. A total of 398 individuals were enrolled in the study, with 200 individuals from low altitude areas and another 198 individuals from high altitude areas. The population studied consisted of students aged 6-18 who regularly use digital devices. Exclusion criteria included children with ocular or systemic diseases, and contact lens users. The materials used in this study included a Snellen chart, slit lamp, Schirmer strip, fluorescein dye for TBUT, clock watch/timer, structured OSDI questionnaire, and data sheet. Initially, we assessed the unaided distance visual acuity using the Snellen chart, while near vision was evaluated at 40 cm. The data collected during this phase were used to determine the best corrected visual acuity. Subsequently, we conducted a slit lamp examination to evaluate corneal opacity or any ocular issues. We also obtained a detailed medical history to determine if the patient wore contact lenses or was taking any medications, with those individuals being excluded from the study. Additionally, we documented the patient's screen time habits. Following these steps, we completed the OSDI questionnaire, along with the Schirmer-test with anesthesia and TBUT test.

Statistical analysis-

The statistical analyses in this research were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23.0, by IBM Corp. Released in 2017. All tests were performed with two-sided hypothesis tests, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. The chi-square test was utilized to test the statistical hypothesis.

Result-

The analysis revealed that the data did not follow a normal distribution. Consequently, non-parametric tests were employed for further analysis. Specifically, the Chi-square test was used to determine any significant differences in the dependent variable between the different groups at low altitude and high altitude. The pie chart is used to plot the gender distribution and it showed that out of total 398 participants that 116 were Male and 84 were female at low altitude and 109 were Male and 89 were female at high altitude.

FIG-1 Gender distribution at high and low altitude.

Across all age groups, children at high altitudes tend to have lower screen time durations compared to those at low altitudes. Younger children (6-9 years) generally have lower screen time. As age increases, particularly in low altitude areas, there is a noticeable increase in screen time duration. The p-value, which indicates statistical significance, is significant at both altitudes with a value of <0.05 .

FIG-2 Graphical representation of age and screen time at high and low altitude.

The data presented in this table clearly demonstrates that high altitude has a substantial negative effect on Tear Breakup Time (TBUT) when screen time is increased. This is evident from the significant decrease in normal TBUT and the corresponding increase in borderline and significant cases. Conversely, at low altitude, screen time has minimal impact on TBUT, with a high proportion of normal TBUT even during longer screen durations. This consistent pattern holds true for both the right and left eyes. The statistical analysis reveals that the p-value for the right eye is significant at a level of less than 0.05, while for the left eye, it is not significant. This confirms the statistical significance of the findings. Consequently, the combination of high altitude and screen time poses a greater risk to ocular health compared to low altitude. This research examines the influence of screen time on tear production, as measured by the Schirmer test-2, at varying altitudes. The findings reveal that individuals at high altitude encounter more significant issues with tear production as their screen time increases, in comparison to those at low altitude. When exposed to 0-2 hours of screen time, a majority of individuals at high altitude exhibit abnormal tear production, with 19 (95%) displaying mild cases and 7 (100%) experiencing moderate cases. Conversely, at low altitude,

44 (23.3%) maintain normal tear production, with only 1 (5%) displaying mild cases and no moderate cases. For 3-5 hours of screen time, only 24 (14.9%) individuals at high altitude maintain normal Schirmer values, while 137 (85.1%) individuals at low altitude maintain normal tear production. At high altitude, there is no available data for screen time exceeding 5 hours, whereas at low altitude, tear production remains relatively unaffected even with extended screen time of up to 11 hours. The p-values indicate a significant difference for the right eye (<0.05), emphasizing the greater impact of high altitude on tear production with screen time. However, the p-value for the left eye is not significant. This highlights the heightened influence of high altitude on tear production when exposed to screen time. (Table-4.4) Notably, at high altitudes, an increase in screen time resulted in higher incidences of mild, moderate, and severe OSDI scores. Prolonged screen exposure of 6-8 hours led to 2 (100%) individuals with normal scores, 2 (100%) with mild scores, 1 (100%) with moderate scores, and 8 (100%) with severe scores. Furthermore, for 9-11 hours of screen exposure, 2 (100%) individuals experienced severe OSDI scores at low altitude. These findings emphasize that prolonged screen exposure exacerbates symptoms more severely at low altitude, with a significant p-value of <0.05 .

Table-1 shows association between Screen time and TBUT of children at low altitude and high altitude.

Association between Screen Time and TBUT								
	Screen Time (hrs)	TBUT	Altitude		Total	p-value		
			Low	High				
R E	0-2	Normal	45 (22.5%)	155 (77.5%)	200	<0.05		
		Borderline	0	12 (100%)	12			
		Significant	0	4 (100%)	4			
		Total	45 (20.8%)	171 (79.2%)	216			
	03-May	Normal	139 (85.8%)	23 (14.2%)	162			
		Borderline	1 (20.0%)	4 (80.0%)	5			
		Total	140 (83.8%)	27 (16.2%)	167			
	06-Aug	Normal	12 (100%)	0	12			
		Significant	1 (100%)	0	1			
		Total	13 (100%)	0	13			
	09-Nov	Normal	1 (100%)	0	1			
		Borderline	1 (100%)	0	1			
		Total	2 (100%)	0	2			
	L E	0-2	Normal	45 (21.7%)	162(78.3%)		207	<0.05
			Borderline	0	7 (100%)		7	
Significant			0	2(100%)	2			
Total			45 (20.8%)	171 (79.2%)	216			
03-May		Normal	140 (84.8%)	25 (15.2%)	165			
		Borderline	0	2 (100%)	2			
		Total	140 (83.8%)	27 (16.2%)	167			
06-Aug		Normal	11 (100%)	0	11			
		Borderline	2 (100%)	0	2			
		Total	13 (100%)	0	13			
09-Nov		Borderline	2 (100%)	0	2			
		Total	2(100%)	0	2			

Table-2 shows association between Screen time and Schirmer test-2 of children at high and low altitude.

Association between Screen Time and Schirmer test-2						p-value
RE	Screen Time (hrs)	Schirmer test-2	Altitude		Total	
			Low	High		
RE	0-2	Normal	44 (23.3%)	145 (76.7%)	189	< 0.05
		Mild	1 (5%)	19 (95%)	20	
		Moderate	0	7 (100%)	7	
		Total	45 (20.8%)	171 (79.2%)	216	
	3-5	Normal	137 (85.1%)	24 (14.9%)	161	
		Mild	3 (60.0%)	2 (40.0%)	5	
		Moderate	0	1 (100%)	1	
		Total	140 (83.8%)	27 (16.2%)	167	
	6-8	Normal	10 (100%)		10	
		Mild	2 (100%)		2	
		Moderate	1 (100%)		1	
		Total	13 (100%)		13	
	9-11	Mild	1 (100%)		1	
		Moderate	1 (100%)		1	
		Total	2 (100%)		2	
	LE	0-2	Normal	45 (22.6%)	154 (77.4%)	
Mild			0	11 (100%)	11	
Moderate			0	6 (100%)	6	
Total			45 (20.8%)	171 (79.2%)	216	
3-5		Normal	135 (84.9%)	24 (15.1%)	159	
		Mild	4 (57.1%)	3 (42.9%)	7	
		Total	139 (83.7%)	27 (16.3%)	166	
6-8		Normal	8 (100%)		8	
		Mild	5 (100%)		5	
		Total	13 (100%)		13	
9-11		Mild	2 (100%)		2	
		Total	2 (100%)		2	

Table 3 shows association between Screen time and OSDI at high and low altitude.

Association between Screen Time and OSDI					
Screen Time (hrs)	Schirmer test-2	Altitude		Total	p-value
		Low	High		
0-2	Normal	16 (11.1%)	128 (88.9%)	144	<0.05
	Mild	17 (32.7%)	35(67.3%)	52	
	Moderate	11 (61.1%)	7 (38.9%)	18	
	Severe	1 (50%)	1 (50%)	2	
	Total	45 (20.8%)	171 (79.2%)	216	
3-5	Normal	32 (69.6%)	14 (30.4%)	46	
	Mild	68 (87.2%)	10 (12.8%)	78	
	Moderate	26 (89.7%)	3 (10.3%)	29	
	Severe	14 (100%)	0	14	
	Total	140 (83.8%)	27 (16.2%)	167	
6-8	Normal	2 (100%)	0	2	
	Mild	2 (100%)	0	2	
	Moderate	1(100%)	0	1	
	Severe	8 (100%)	0	8	
	Total	13 (100%)	0	13	
9-11	Severe	2 (100%)	0	2	
	Total	2 (100%)	0	2	

Discussion-

The current investigation was conducted to explore the relationship between dry eye and screen time in school-going children, with a specific focus on the disparities observed at high and low altitudes. The outcomes of this study provide valuable insights into the diverse effects

of screen time on tear film stability, tear production, and overall ocular surface health. In recent years, the prevalence of dry eye disease (DED) in children has increased due to the growing popularity of electronic devices. During the COVID-19 pandemic, academic activities in schools and universities were conducted online in many countries, resulting in prolonged exposure of children's eyes to screens and electronic gadgets (Neti, N. et al 2021). At high altitudes, individuals with minimal screen time predominantly had normal OSDI scores, whereas symptoms noticeably increased with longer screen time. Specifically, a significant majority of individuals who spent 0-2 hours on screens had normal OSDI scores at high altitudes, whereas individuals with mild, moderate, and severe symptoms were observed at both altitudes to a similar extent. Prolonged screen exposure (3-11 hours) consistently worsened OSDI scores, particularly at low altitudes, indicating a strong correlation between increased screen time and exacerbated ocular surface disease symptoms. This correlation was supported by a highly significant p-value of <0.05 . In the study conducted by DeCook, N. (2019), it was observed that 21 children out of 33 in the older child category were using electronic devices significantly. These subjects reported higher than recommended average device usage, with an average of 5.17 ± 5.18 hours on weekdays and 6.86 ± 6.60 hours on weekends. Among them, five subjects exhibited a significant TBUT of five seconds or less, while 11 subjects showed borderline TBUT of less than 10 seconds but more than 5 seconds. The research was carried out on the pediatric population of Michigan.

Our research findings suggest that screen time has a significant impact on tear breakup time (TBUT) at high altitude, resulting in moderate to severe TBUT across all screen time categories. In contrast, individuals at low altitude maintain normal TBUT even with increased

screen time, indicating minimal impact. These results emphasize that the negative effects of screen time on eye health are exacerbated at high altitude compared to low altitude.

In a study conducted by Akib et al. (2021), the relationship between prolonged smartphone use and the incidence of dry eye among junior high school students aged 12-16 years was examined. The study included 143 participants and found a significant association between the duration of smartphone use and dry eye. The Schirmer test showed a p-value of less than 0.01, indicating a significant relationship. Additionally, other measures such as TBUT, OSDI scores, abnormal blink rate, and TMH also showed p-values less than 0.01, further supporting the link between smartphone use and dry eye

The impact of screen time on tear production, particularly at high altitudes, is evident based on the results of the Schirmer test-2. Individuals at high altitudes experienced a higher prevalence of mild and moderate dry eye with increased screen time, whereas those at low altitudes had a higher occurrence of normal tear production even with longer screen time. The statistical analysis revealed that there were significant differences between altitudes for the right eye (p-value <0.05), indicating that tear production was affected by altitude. However, for the left eye, the difference was not statistically significant.

Conclusion-

Children in high-altitude areas spend less time on screens, especially younger children. However, as children get older, screen time increases in low-altitude areas.. Prolonged screen exposure is associated with ocular symptoms, especially in low-altitude regions. Children with longer screen time have a higher incidence of Dry Eye Disease (DED), regardless of altitude. Research indicates that screen time and age impact eye health differently at varying altitudes.Children

in high-altitude areas spend less time on screens but are at higher risk for eye issues like Dry Eye Disease. It is important to develop strategies to regulate screen time and address eye health concerns, particularly for children in high-altitude regions.

References-

1. K. Khurana, Comprehensive Ophthalmology, 9th edition.
2. Akib, M. N., Pirade, S. R., Syawal, S. R., Fauzan, M. M., Eka, H., & Seweng, A. (2021). Association between prolonged use of smartphone and the incidence of dry eye among junior high school students. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 11, 100761.
3. Albietz, J. M. (2000). Prevalence of dry eye subtypes in clinical optometry practice. *Optometry and Vision Science*, 77(7), 357-363.
4. Alnahdi W, Hadrawi M, Danish E, et al. Relationship Between Screen Time and Dry Eye Symptoms During the COVID-19 Pandemic in the Pediatric Population of the Western Region of Saudi Arabia. *Cureus*. 2022 Nov;14(11):e31015. DOI: 10.7759/cureus.31015. PMID: 36475117; PMCID: PMC9717719.
5. American Optometric Association. (1995). Guide to the clinical aspects of computer vision syndrome. *St. Louis: American Optometric Association*, 1.
6. Bahkir, F. A., & Grandee, S. S. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 lockdown on digital device-related ocular health. *Indian journal of ophthalmology*, 68(11), 2378-2383.

7. Begley, C. G., Himebaugh, N., Renner, D., Liu, H., Chalmers, R., Simpson, T., & Varikooty, J. (2006). Tear breakup dynamics: a technique for quantifying tear film instability. *Optometry and vision science*, *83*(1), 15-21.
8. Bron, A. J., de Paiva, C. S., Chauhan, S. K., Bonini, S., Gabison, E. E., Jain, S., ... & Sullivan, D. A. (2017). TFOS DEWS II pathophysiology report. *The ocular surface*, *15*(3), 438-510.
9. Cecilia, N. C. Alvan'D ON.(2022) Correlation Between Dry Eye and Screen Viewing Time Among Young Adult. *J Ophthalmic Res Vis Care*, *2*(1).
10. CHOUHAN, D., PARMAR, B., OJHA, B., & KHANDELWAL, G. (2023). EFFECTS OF COMPUTER VISION SYNDROME ON TEAR FILM QUALITY OF INDIVIDUALS ACROSS VARIOUS AGE GROUPS AND OCCUPATIONS. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*, *16*(8), 153-156.
11. Chaturvedi, N., Singh, P., & Bhattacharya, M. (2022). Screen exposure time and computer vision syndrome in school-age children during COVID-19 era: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Clinical Ophthalmology and Research*, *10*(3), 105-109.
12. Chidi-Egboka, N. C., Briggs, N. E., Jalbert, I., & Golebiowski, B. (2019). The ocular surface in children: A review of current knowledge and meta-analysis of tear film stability and tear secretion in children. *The Ocular Surface*, *17*(1), 28-39.
13. Craig, J. P., Nichols, K. K., Akpek, E. K., Caffery, B., Dua, H. S., Joo, C. K., ... & Stapleton, F. (2017). TFOS DEWS II definition and classification report. *The ocular surface*, *15*(3), 276-283.
14. DeCook, N. (2019). Correlation Between Dry Eye and Screen Time in Children.

15. Gangamma, M. P., & Rajagopala, M. (2010). A clinical study on “Computer vision syndrome” and its management with Triphala eye drops and Saptamrita Lauha. *AYU (An international quarterly journal of research in Ayurveda)*, 31(2), 236-239.
16. Gupta, N., Prasad, I., Himashree, G., & D'Souza, P. (2008). Prevalence of dry eye at high altitude: a case controlled comparative study. *High altitude medicine & biology*, 9(4), 327-334.
17. García-Ayuso, D., Di Pierdomenico, J., Moya-Rodríguez, E., Valiente-Soriano, F. J., Galindo-Romero, C., & Sobrado-Calvo, P. (2022). Assessment of dry eye symptoms among university students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Clinical & experimental optometry*, 105(5), 507–513.
18. Junghans, B. M., Azizoglu, S., & Crewther, S. G. (2020). Unexpectedly high prevalence of asthenopia in Australian school children identified by the CISS survey tool. *BMC ophthalmology*, 20(1), 408. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12886-020-01642-3>
19. K. S., Schaumberg, D., Uchino, M., Vehof, J., Viso, E., Vitale, S., & Jones, L. (2017). TFOS DEWS II Epidemiology Report. *The ocular surface*, 15(3), 334–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtos.2017.05.003>
20. Karaküçük, S., & Mirza, G. E. (2000). Ophthalmological effects of high altitude. *Ophthalmic research*, 32(1), 30-40.
21. Koh, S., & Rhee, M. K. (2021). COVID-19 and dry eye. *Eye & Contact Lens*, 47(6), 317-322.
22. Li, N., Deng, X. G., & He, M. F. (2012). Comparison of the Schirmer I test with and without topical anesthesia for diagnosing dry eye. *International journal of ophthalmology*, 5(4), 478.

23. Loh, K. Y., & Redd, S. C. (2008). Understanding and preventing computer vision syndrome. *Malaysian family physician: the official journal of the Academy of Family Physicians of Malaysia*, 3(3), 128.
24. Liu, B., Zhou, D., Li, Z., Wang, Y., & Chen, Z. (2023). A survey on the degree of eye discomfort caused by video terminal use among college students in different altitudes. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), 1209.
25. Liu, B., Jiang, S., Li, Z., Wang, Y., Zhou, D., & Chen, Z. (2022). Investigation and analysis of Eye Discomfort caused by Video Display Terminal Use among Medical Students studying at high-altitude regions. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 900539.
26. Mader, T. H., & Tabin, G. (2003). Going to high altitude with preexisting ocular conditions. *High Altitude Medicine & Biology*, 4(4), 419-430.
27. Moon, J. H., Kim, K. W., & Moon, N. J. (2016). Smartphone use is a risk factor for pediatric dry eye disease according to region and age: a case control study. *BMC ophthalmology*, 16, 1-7
28. Moss, S. E., Klein, R., & Klein, B. E. (2000). Prevalence of and risk factors for dry eye syndrome. *Archives of ophthalmology*, 118(9), 1264-1268.
29. Neti, N., Prabhasawat, P., Chirapapaisan, C., & Ngowyutagon, P. (2021). Provocation of dry eye disease symptoms during COVID-19 lockdown. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 24434
30. Qu, X. M., & Chu, R. Y. (2005). Take high of the study of VDT related eye symptoms. *[Zhonghua yan ke za Zhi] Chinese Journal of Ophthalmology*, 41(11), 963-965.

31. Ranasinghe, P., Wathurapatha, W. S., Perera, Y. S., Lamabadusuriya, D. A., Kulatunga, S., Jayawardana, N., & Katulanda, P. (2016). Computer vision syndrome among computer office workers in a developing country: an evaluation of prevalence and risk factors. *BMC research notes*, 9, 150. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-016-1962-1>
32. Riaz, S., Mirza, U. T., & Khan, M. T. The Frequency of Tear Film Abnormalities Among Medical Students Of 4th Year MBBS Class. *Al-Shifa Journal of Ophthalmology*, 124.
33. Stapleton, F., Alves, M., Bunya, V. Y., Jalbert, I., Lekhanont, K., Malet, F., ... & Jones, L. (2017). Tfos dewes ii epidemiology report. *The ocular surface*, 15(3), 334-365.
34. Toda, I., Fujishima, H., & Tsubota, K. (1993). Ocular fatigue is the major symptom of dry eye. *Acta ophthalmologica*, 71(3), 347-352.
35. Tripathi, A., Agarwal, R., & Kharya, P. (2022). Dry eye disease related to digital screen exposure in medical students. *The Pan-American Journal of Ophthalmology*, 4(1), 35.
36. ubota, K. (2018). Short tear film breakup time–type dry eye. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*, 59(14), DES64-DES70.
37. Usgaonkar, U., Parkar, S. R. S., & Shetty, A. (2021). Impact of the use of digital devices on eyes during the lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *Indian journal of ophthalmology*, 69(7), 1901-1906.

38. Wadhvani, M., Manika, M., Jajoo, M., & Upadhyay, A. D. (2022). Online survey to assess computer vision syndrome in children due to excessive screen exposure during the COVID 19 pandemic lockdown. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 11(9), 5387-5392.
39. Wang, M. T., Murphy, P. J., Blades, K. J., & Craig, J. P. (2018). Comparison of non-invasive tear film stability measurement techniques. *Clinical and Experimental Optometry*, 101(1), 13-17.
40. Zahid, M., Rehmat, M., & Imtiaz, H. (2023). Association Between Screen Time and Tear Film Stability: Screen Time and Tear Film Stability. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences*, 29-